

Electrically charged PCM thermal storage solution for CSP plants

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1. Introduction

In order to reduce global warming, renewable technologies have become a major trend. The financial investment only in 2022 in these technologies was almost 500 USD billion [1] and the cumulative investment between 2016 and 2050 is expected to be between 13 and 38 USD trillion [2], depending on the selected scenario. Among renewable technologies, solar photovoltaic and wind technologies have experienced an extremely rapid growth, implementing more than 910 TW and almost 600 TW of installed capacity respectively in the 2013-2022 period, having a final share of more than 57% of the total renewable installed capacity worldwide [3]. While both technologies are making the transition from fossil fuels to renewables fast and economically efficient, there is a limit on how much non-dispatchable technology a grid can withstand without problems [4]. On the other hand, Concentrated Solar Power technology (CSP) with Thermal Energy Storage (TES) is a dispatchable renewable technology that can support grid safety mechanisms such as frequency control, time shifting or transmission congestion relief, and it can also act as an upgrade deferral, or be used for long duration energy storage.

Nowadays CSP technology has been widely implemented, but its cost is too high to compete with other non-dispatchable renewable technologies [5]. Nevertheless, it has the potential to reduce its cost when coupled with advanced thermal cycles for electricity generation. In this work, an innovative thermal energy storage that can be implemented in state-of-the-art CSP plants is presented, able to reach operating temperatures up to 610 °C and enabling the use of supercritical CO₂ power cycles. This TES is based on Phase Change Material (PCM) technology improved with metal wools for thermal conductivity enhancement and for its use as built-in electric heaters, enabling the TES system capacity to work as a power to heat reservoir and to further increase the capacity factor of the plant while improving grid stability services at the same time. These electric heaters grant the CSP plant the ability to hybridise with other collocated renewable technologies, typically photovoltaic, or even from the grid with PPAs.

2. Storage system

2.1 Heat transfer fluid

To be able to implement the proposed TES solution in state-of-the-art CSP plants, the authors have decided to use the traditional molten salts (40/60 wt% KNO₃/NaNO₃) as Heat Transfer Fluid (HTF). This binary salt has been extensively used at commercial level, but always limiting its maximum temperature to 565 °C to avoid degradation phenomena. This degradation mechanism is a time-related mechanism, where, as described by Bell et al. [6] and McConohy et al [7], the decomposition occurs when salts are kept at high temperatures for a prolonged period of time. This degradation decomposes the original sodium and potassium nitrates into nitrites and other components that can lead to high corrosion rates, while at the same time changes the thermal stability of the salt reducing its real operative temperature [6]. In commercial plants, salts are used as HTF and as storage medium at the same time, and thus the residence time of the salt at maximum temperature is in the order of magnitude of hours, leading to the issues pointed above if the maximum temperature is not limited. To solve this problem, the authors only use the solar salt as HTF, storing the energy in a PCM. This allows to increase the maximum operative temperature of the salts up to 610°C for small periods of time without degradation.

2.2 Storage media

Even when phase change materials have been extensively studied by the academia due to their high energy density and potential low cost, there are some issues that need to be solved before its commercial implementation. One of the main issues is the low thermal conductivity of these materials, typically around 0.5 W/mK [8]. Several options have been studied by different authors to solve this issue, from the use of fins, metal or graphite composites to nano-particles or nano-additives [8]–[10], but all these solutions have in common an important increase in final costs. Taking this into consideration, the authors have selected to use cheap metal fibres called metal wools inside the PCM as heat transfer enhancement, forming a metal wool - inorganic salt composite. The preliminary results at laboratory level showed very promising results, achieving thermal conductivities of around 4.66 W/mK in the direction of the metal wools fibres and around 0.77 W/mK in the perpendicular direction [11]. This anisotropic configuration maximizes the melting in the direction of the fibres and a stable melting front in the vertical direction, making this TES able to behave like a thermocline, homogenising the temperatures horizontally while allowing temperature gradients vertically (vertical configuration).

The typical operation temperatures of a CSP plant with a steam power cycle go from 290°C, restricted by the solidification temperature of the solar salt, up to 565°C restricted by the degradation phenomena described before. For the implementation of supercritical CO₂ cycles, temperatures up to 610°C are required, which implies a thermal gradient of 320°C. This high thermal gradient imposes a penalty on a latent heat storage system, and thus a cascade configuration is proposed. The cascade is made

by selecting the appropriate PCM with an adequate melting temperature in a range of melting temperatures from 300°C to 600°C. Each PCM module is then responsible for providing the energy of a smaller thermal gradient and, by taking advantage of the thermocline configuration, this energy is provided by latent and sensible heat throughout the whole working temperature range of the module (Figure 1). As can be seen in this figure, the cascade configuration allows for a much lower temperature difference between the charge and discharge phases.

Figure 1 Distribution of sensible and latent heat in a PCM heat exchanger. Left, only 1 PCM. Right, 4 PCM modules for the same temperature range

This configuration also solves the issue of thermal shocks in the module by reducing the temperature difference between the HTF and the storage media. The final selection of the PCM candidates and the corrosion-compatibility metal wools pairs is still under development. Up to know, in the work carried out in the HYBRIDplus project from where this investigation has been carried out, up to 67 PCM candidates have been identified in this temperature range, with promising initial corrosion compatibility test results.

2.3 Storage configuration

Each PCM module -defined by the melting temperature of the PCM- can be composed of a different number of tanks in order to cope with the different melting enthalpy per mass of each selected material. Each tank follows a vertical configuration of a traditional shell and tube heat exchanger, with the HTF flowing through the tubes and the PCM-metal wool mixture stored in the shell, with a preferential horizontal distribution of the fibres of the metal wool. Depending on the selected hybridization mechanism, the final configuration varies: for traditional immersion electric heaters, the electric resistance uses a portion of the tubes; for ohmic heating, electrodes are positioned in the tubes and the shell; and for magnetic charge, an external element is added to the shell to generate the magnetic currents.

Figure 2 PCM tank configuration. 1) Cover gas for volumetric expansion. 2) Tube registry. 3) Metal wool. 4) HTF header

3. Charging mechanisms

This storage system can be charged both electrically and thermally, and the discharge is done thermally using the HTF to feed the sCO₂ power cycle. Once considering the power cycle, the final configuration becomes a power-to-heat-to-power system, also known as Carnot Battery, if charged electrically or a heat-to-power when charged through the solar field.

3.1 Thermal charge

The preferred charging mechanism for the TES is through the heat provided by the solar field of the solar plant, transferred using the molten salt HTF to the cascade PCM. The solar salt flows through the tubes of the modules, from top to bottom, where its energy is extracted with the help of the metal wools as heat transfer enhancers. The PCM cascade behaves as a parallel/series configuration, where the HTF is distributed in parallel among the different containers of the same PCM, to then go in series to the next temperature level PCM batch of containers. With this configuration each module behaves as a thermocline, while at the same time, the whole PCM cascade also behaves as a thermocline. To fully accomplish a thermocline behaviour with no abrupt temperature changes, each temperature level module cannot be fully charged. In each temperature module a full range of temperature is present, with the lower part of the PCM in a solidified state at the lowest tank temperature even after the charging process is finished. Although this implies a reduction in the total amount of energy stored per module, this configuration strongly reduces the mechanical problems of thermal stress for large temperature gradients between the PCM and the HTF at the start of the discharging process. The same principle applies on discharge, where the PCM module is considered to be fully discharged, even though a small portion in the upper part remains in overheated liquid state.

3.2 Immersion heater electric charge

Commercial molten salt tanks in CSP plants use immersion electric heaters to avoid reaching temperatures where the solar salt could start freezing. This configuration is expected to be used only as a safety mechanism. However, the same principle could be used to provide power-to-heat if the configuration is rearranged and the design is improved. This is done in the proposed TES concept by inserting these immersion heaters as tubes into the shell-and-tube module configuration. Thanks to the use of metal wools as heat enhancers, the main challenge of the design of the immersion heaters for power-to-heat is overcome. However, the use of physical space to insert the immersion heaters poses a challenge in the design, reducing the effective transfer area when the module is thermally charged and increasing the total volume of the tanks, leading to an increase in total costs both due to both required area and due to material usage.

3.3 Ohmic heating electric charge

The main mechanism behind the immersion heaters is to pass a current through a conductor, typically a metal filament, to produce heat due to the Joule effect. This filament is normally encapsulated in an electrically insulated sheath to avoid deteriorating the filament and ensuring the right path for the electricity. Nevertheless, this encapsulation is not mandatory if the path for the current is provided. By using the heat enhancers metal wools as filaments, the same Joule effect, or ohmic heating, is achieved when a current is generated between the shell of the module and the tubes. The metal wools need to be arranged in a way to grant the shortest path between electrodes, which is in a horizontal configuration in a vertical tank, the same as the required configuration for the thermocline, and the continuity of the circuit needs to be granted. Direct contact between the tubes and the metal wools is required, same as between the metal wools and the shell. This poses a challenge by itself since a small gap could lead to electric arcs, which could easily and quickly deteriorate the metal components. Another identified challenge is the different electric conductivity of the PCM while in solid state and in liquid state, and in particular, during the melting phase, which makes difficult the control of the required voltages.

3.4 Magnetic charge

An alternating magnetic field can be used to induce an electric current in the metal wool, which in turn generates thermal power by Joule effect. The magnetic field is externally generated by a coil surrounding each PCM module without requiring direct contact, and, as such, without increasing the internal volume of the tank. The presence of the metal wool ensures a proper internal distribution of the induced currents, but to avoid those currents in the shell, a specific study on non-ferrous materials needs to be carried out. Another challenge of this configuration is the requirement of power electronics. On one hand these electronics can compensate the power factor of the electric grid by harmonic distortion correction and other voltage quality improvements, but on the other hand the presence of power electronics increases the TES cost.

4. Concept demonstration

With the aim of proving the TES concept explained here, the University of Seville is planning to build in its premises a pilot plant with three PCM modules with different melting temperatures, capable of demonstrating at pilot level (TRL5-6) the cascade concept coupled with the thermocline concept. The modules will be built as explained above, in a shell-and-tube configuration with molten salt used as HTF passing through the tubes and the PCM stored in the shell. Each module is planned to be electrified in a different way, one using immersion heaters, another one with ohmic heating and the last one using magnetic charge. To simulate the thermal charge, a circuit of solar salt will be installed, with a hot and cold tank, an in-line electric heater and a cooler. The pilot plant will have different path configurations for versatility, and the design temperature of the whole system will be 600 °C. Even though the final configuration is expected to test the three different modules simultaneously, the installation will be sequential, performing test independently with each of the modules before the whole system integration. The order of implementation will follow the degree of innovation of the electric heating system along with the temperature level, implementing first the low melting temperature PCM with the enhanced immersion heaters, then the medium melting temperature PCM with ohmic heating and last the high melting temperature PCM with the magnetic induction mechanism. All modules will include the metal wool heat enhancer element and the lesson learnt on the previous modules will be applied to the following ones.

5. Conclusions

This document presents the innovative PCM-TES to be proved in the framework of the HYBRIDplus project, including different mechanisms for hybridization through power-to-heat mechanisms.

- Metal wool is a suitable candidate for thermal transfer enhancement of the PCM.
- The cascade configuration can improve the behaviour of the TES, by reducing the temperature difference between charge and discharge.
- The thermocline concept is used both at the module and the cascade level, ensuring a smooth continuity in temperature gradients and reducing thermal shocks.
- Temperatures up to 610 °C are achievable with actual solar salt technology and are required to efficiently operate supercritical CO₂ power cycles.
- Three different hybridization mechanisms are presented highlighting the challenges that each of them poses for its use in the PCM-TES system.

6. Acknowledgement

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101084182.

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